

METHOD OF CALCULATION OF SOLAR HEAT SUPPLY SYSTEMS AND ASSESSMENT OF THEIR EFFICIENCY

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Abstract. *This article examines a calculation methodology for year-round solar heating systems. Key solar system parameters are determined, including the available solar energy, the heat load for heating and hot water supply, the solar field area, and the volume of the heat accumulator. The energy, thermal engineering, and technical and economic performance of the solar heating system are assessed. Annual fossil fuel savings are determined, and the system's payback period is presented.*

Keywords: *solar heating systems, solar system, solar radiation, solar collectors, heat load, heat accumulator, fuel savings, technical and economic efficiency, payback period.*

Introduction

In today's environment of rising energy consumption and costs, the use of renewable energy sources in heating systems is particularly relevant. One of the most promising areas is the use of solar heating systems, which reduce fossil fuel consumption, minimize harmful emissions, and increase the energy independence of various facilities. Solar heating systems are widely used for heating and hot water supply in residential, public, and industrial buildings. Their efficiency is largely determined by climatic conditions, solar radiation levels, the correct selection of the design and energy parameters of the solar system, and its operating mode. Therefore, it is necessary to perform a sound thermal engineering and technical and economic analysis of solar heating systems.

Thermal calculations for solar installations are complicated by the variability of meteorological factors, such as solar radiation intensity, outdoor temperature, and sunshine duration. Therefore, in practice, aggregated calculation methods are used, which allow the main parameters of the system to be determined with sufficient accuracy, including the area of the solar field, the volume of the heat accumulator, and the expected annual fuel savings. The aim of this study is to develop and apply a calculation method for a year-round solar heating system, as well as to evaluate its energy and technical-economic efficiency. The study determines the optimal parameters of solar collectors, the volume of storage devices, capital and operating costs, and the payback period of the solar system compared to traditional heating systems.

Literary analysis. The issues of using solar energy in heating systems are discussed in detail in a number of scientific and regulatory sources. V. V. Kirillov's methodological guide [1] provides the fundamentals of designing seasonal solar hot water systems, discussing the principles of selecting solar collectors, connection diagrams, and the operating features of solar systems. The author emphasizes the importance of correctly determining the heat load and the parameters of storage devices to ensure stable system operation. The designer's handbook edited by I. G. Staroverov [2] contains general information on the calculation of heating and hot water supply systems for buildings. This source presents methods for determining heat loads, which are used,

among other things, in the design of solar heating systems as additional or autonomous sources of thermal energy.

The regulatory document SNiP II-34-76 "Hot Water Supply" [3] establishes the basic requirements for the design of hot water supply systems, including design temperatures, water flow rates, and sanitary and technical standards. This document is used to justify the parameters of solar hot water systems and their integration with traditional heat sources. The fundamental principles of calculating solar heating systems are presented in the work of W. Beckman, S. Klein, and J. Duffy [4]. The book describes methods for determining incoming solar radiation, the thermal efficiency of solar collectors, and annual thermal energy production. This source is widely used in the thermal engineering calculations of solar systems and the assessment of their energy efficiency.

The collective monograph "Solar Heating and Cooling Systems" edited by E. V. Sarnatsky and S. A. Chistovich [5] examines various solar installation designs, heat accumulation issues, and the specifics of their application in various climatic conditions. The authors note that the efficiency of solar systems significantly depends on the correct selection of design and energy parameters. N. V. Kharchenko's work [6] focuses on individual solar heating and hot water systems. The practical aspects of designing and operating solar systems, as well as their technical and economic indicators, are examined. It is emphasized that the use of solar systems can reduce the consumption of traditional energy resources and improve the energy efficiency of buildings. Thus, an analysis of the literature reviewed demonstrates that solar heating systems are a technically and economically feasible solution. However, their design requires careful thermal engineering calculations taking into account climatic conditions, regulatory requirements, and operating modes, which determines the relevance of this study.

Materials and Methods. Calculating solar heating systems (SHS) [4] involves determining:

- the available solar energy;
- the heating load for heating and hot water supply;
- the energy and geometric characteristics of the solar system;
- the volume of the heat storage device;
- annual fuel savings;
- the technical and economic indicators of the solar system.

The available solar energy [4] is determined based on the total and diffuse solar radiation received by the surface of the solar receiver. Accurately calculating the thermal energy of a solar installation is complicated by the influence of climatic factors. Therefore, aggregated methods are typically used to determine the main SHS parameters – the surface area of the solar field, the volume of the storage devices, and the estimated annual fuel savings. Since the heat supply system operates year-round, and therefore the thermal load in winter will exceed that in summer, the thermal calculation of the solar system must be performed for winter. To ensure maximum heat output, solar collectors are typically installed at an angle to the horizontal, at an optimal tilt angle. The solar collector tilt angle is calculated using the formula [1-4]:

$$\beta = \varphi \pm \delta_a \quad (1)$$

where φ – latitude of the area;

δ_a – average declination of the sun for the period under consideration.

$$\delta = 23,45 \cdot \sin \left(360 \cdot \frac{284+n}{365} \right) \quad (2)$$

where n – ordinal number of the day of the year.

The intensity Q_{ins} of incident solar radiation on an inclined surface oriented in the southern direction can be determined by the formula [1-6]:

$$Q_{ins} = K_1 \cdot S + K_2 \cdot D + K_3 \cdot (S + D) \cdot \rho \quad (3)$$

where S – intensity of direct solar radiation incident on a horizontal surface, MJ/m²;

D – intensity of diffuse incident solar radiation on a horizontal surface, MJ/m²;

ρ – albedo of the underlying surface;

K_1, K_2, K_3 – correlation coefficients.

$$K_2 = \cos^2 \frac{m}{2} \quad (4)$$

$$K_3 = \sin^2 \frac{m}{2} \quad (5)$$

The coefficient K_1 depends on the latitude of the area, the angle of inclination of the SC and the time of year.

Results and discussion.

Knowing the estimated consumer heat load Q^{year} and the amount of incoming solar radiation Q_{ins} (MJ/m²), we can determine the solar field area $F_{f.a.}$, the required number of solar panels N SC, and the storage tank volume V_{TV} :

$$F_{f.a} = \frac{Q^{year}}{Q_{ins} \cdot \eta_{SC}} \quad (6)$$

$$N = \frac{F_{f.a}}{F_{SC}} \quad (7)$$

$$V_{TV} = 0,07 F_{f.a}$$

where η_{SC} – average seasonal efficiency of the SC, $\eta=0,5$;

N – number of solar collectors, pieces;

F_{SC} – area of one SC, m².

Capital costs for a solar heating system are determined by the formula:

$$K_{f.a} = C_{SC} \cdot F_{f.a} + C_{AE} + C_{TV} \cdot V_{TV} \quad (8)$$

where C_{SC} – unit cost of insurance, sum;

C_{AE} – unit cost of auxiliary equipment, pipelines, control valves; instrumentation and automation systems, etc., sum;

C_{TV} – unit cost of TV, sum.

Operating costs for the solar system $\mathfrak{A}_{G.S}$ consist of annual expenses for repair and maintenance of equipment [1-4]:

$$\mathfrak{A}_{f.a} = \mathfrak{A}_{t.r} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathfrak{A}_{t.r}$ – annual costs for repair and maintenance of equipment.

The given costs are determined by the formula:

$$\Pi_{f.a} E_n \cdot K_{f.a} + \mathfrak{A}_{f.a} \quad (10)$$

The annual savings of organic fuel $B_{\mathfrak{A}}^m$ [5] and material costs 3_{en}^m for it during the operation of a solar system are calculated according to the formulas:

$$B_{\mathfrak{A}}^m = \frac{f \cdot Q^n}{Q_{II}^{-p} \cdot \eta_{II}^{-p}} \quad (11)$$

$$3_{en}^m = (3_{z.en}^m + 3_{u.e}^{mp}) \cdot B_{\mathfrak{A}}^m \quad (12)$$

where f – replacement rate. To decide on the cost-effectiveness of the options under consideration, it is necessary to compare capital and operating costs using the payback period determined by the formula:

$$T_{OK} = \frac{K_{f.a} - K_{m.c}}{U_{m.c} - U_{f.a}} \quad (13)$$

where $K_{f.a}$. – capital investment for the option using a solar system, sum;
 $K_{m.c}$. – capital investment for the option using a traditional heating system, sum;
 $U_{m.c}$. – total annual costs for the option using a traditional heating system, sum;
 $U_{f.a}$. – total annual costs for the option using a solar system, sum [1-5].

Table 1.

Key design parameters of the solar heating system.

Indicator Name	Designation	Meaning	Unit of measurement
Annual Thermal Load	Q_{year}	80–90	GJ/year
Total Solar Radiation on a Horizontal Surface	$S + D$	≈ 1500	MJ/m ² ·year
Solar Radiation on an Inclined Surface	Q_{ins}	1700–1800	MJ/m ² ·year
Average Seasonal Efficiency of Solar Collectors	η_{sc}	0,5	–
Estimated Solar Field Area	$F_{f.a}$	90–105	m ²
Area of a Single Solar Collector	F_{sc}	2,0	m ²
Number of Solar Collectors	N	45–52	pieces
Heat Storage Tank Volume	V_{TV}	6,0–7,5	m ³
Fuel Replacement Factor	f	0,5–0,6	–
Annual Fossil Fuel Savings	B_3^m	2,0–3,0	tons of fuel equivalent/year

Based on the calculated data presented in Table 1, an assessment was made of the key technical parameters of a solar heating system designed to provide a building with year-round thermal energy. The annual heat load of the heating and hot water supply system is assumed to be 80–90 GJ/year, which is typical for residential and public buildings in areas with moderate to high solar activity. The solar heating system calculation was based on approximate climatic and thermal data typical for regions with medium to high solar activity. The system under consideration is designed to heat a building year-round. The average annual total solar radiation incident on a horizontal surface is assumed to be

$$S + D \approx 1500 \text{ MJ/m}^2.$$

Taking into account the optimal angle of inclination of the solar collectors and their orientation in the southern direction, the calculated value of solar radiation falling on the inclined surface was

$$Q_f \approx 1700\text{--}1800 \text{ MJ/m}^2 \text{ in the year.}$$

The annual heat load of the heating and hot water supply system is assumed to be equal to $Q_{year} \approx 80\text{--}90 \text{ GJ}$.

With an average seasonal efficiency of solar collectors $\eta_{SC} = 0.5$, the calculated area of the heliofield was about

$$F_{h,p} \approx 90-105 \text{ m}^2.$$

When using solar collectors with a module area of $F_{SC} \approx 2.0 \text{ m}^2$, the estimated number of collectors was $N \approx 45-52$. The volume of the heat storage tank, determined using the aggregated dependence, was $V_{TV} \approx 6.0-7.5 \text{ m}^3$. The capital costs of the solar heating system were estimated, taking into account the cost of solar collectors, a storage tank, and auxiliary equipment. Operating costs for the year were assumed to be minimal and include equipment maintenance and repair costs. The annual fossil fuel savings, with a replacement factor of $f \approx 0.5-0.6$, amounted to approximately 2.0–3.0 tons of equivalent fuel per year. This demonstrates a significant reduction in the consumption of traditional energy resources and a reduction in operating costs.

Conclusions. This paper examines a comprehensive calculation methodology for a year-round solar heating system based on estimated climate data. Key solar system parameters, including the solar field area and the volume of the heat storage tank, are determined. It is shown that, with an average seasonal solar collector efficiency of approximately 0.5, the use of a solar heating system results in fossil fuel savings of 2.0–3.0 tons of equivalent fuel per year. The estimated payback period for the solar system is 7–10 years. These results confirm the feasibility of using solar heating systems in regions with sufficient solar radiation and can be used in pre-design calculations.

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